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INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS EVALUATION: OVERVIEW OF METHODS AND APPROACHES

Abstract. The study focuses on assessing investment attractiveness. The article examines different approaches to investment attractiveness evaluation, such as multidimensional ranking, taxonomic analysis, factors analysis, SWOT analysis etc. The research also considers the effect of Russia's full-scale invasion in Ukraine on investment attractiveness. The article conducts a comparative analysis of methods for evaluating investment attractiveness, with information clearly systematized in table. Multidimensional ranking was used to analyze investment attractiveness, and statistical information was visualized. The approach of economic and statistical analysis is described in detail, which is based on the use of statistical data to assess the economic indicators of a region or country. Key methods of this analysis include: analysis of main macroeconomic indicators: GDP, inflation rate, unemployment, export-import dynamics, economic growth rates and analysis of investment flows, in particular assessment of the volumes of foreign direct investment entering the country or region and their dynamics

Keywords: investment attractiveness, evaluation, methods and approaches, multidimensional ranking, taxonomic analysis, statistics methods

Formulation of the problem. Investment attractiveness has always been in the center of attention of officials. Investment attractiveness is an important prerequisite for identifying and forming the competitive advantages of the region. So it's very important to consider the different ways, methods and approaches to its evaluation. Obviously, attracting investment into the regional economy is one of the priority tasks in the context of post-war recovery. This task can be optimally realized by increasing

the investment attractiveness of the region for potential investors and developing a plan now, during the war.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The study of investment attractiveness has received special attention from many scientists all around the world. In particular, Khamitova Mamlakat N. in [1] analyzes the investment attractiveness in different countries, Shakhriyor M. in [2] describes the directions for improving the investment environment and Nozimov E. in [3] suggests the ways of increasing investment attractiveness of the region. Investment attractiveness is considered in different areas, objects. So, Boichenko E. and Martynovych N. in [4] analyse investment attractiveness of territories, Danylyshyn B. and co-authors in [5] - regions, Vdovyn M. and Liubovetska D. in [6] - types of economic activities and Demishev I. and Voitko S. in [7] - Ukraine in general. Researchers use different methodologies to assess socio-economic processes, investment attractiveness and others. Multi-criteria decision-making methods are used in [8,9], fuzzy logic methods in [10], multidimensional ranking and taxonomic analysis in [11,12]. However, the analysis of investment attractiveness evaluation methods is relevant and requires further research.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. A variety of factors influence the investment attractiveness of regions, with key ones being economic, social, political, and others. Different factors require different approaches to evaluate investment attractiveness. The diversity of statistical and mathematical methods helps us to account for the various evaluation and modeling features. However, it is important to systematize and characterize these methods, techniques, and approaches.

Formulation of the goals of the article (statement of the task). The purpose of the research is to systematize methods and approaches of investment attractiveness evaluation.

Research methods. The research uses the methods of statistical modelling, in particular taxonomic analysis and multidimensional ranking. It is also considered a group of methods, which help to evaluate the investment attractiveness. Special attention is also paid to such general methods of scientific research as analysis.

Presentation of the main research material. The economic development of a country largely depends on the progress of its regions. Investments in the regional economy contribute to increased employment, higher wages, and profitability of enterprises, which, in turn, increases budget revenues. This leads to improved well-being of the population and ensures socio-economic development. That's why it is important to consider the different methods and approaches to assessment of investment attractiveness.

There are several methods and approaches for assessing investment attractiveness, such as:

1. Economic and statistical analysis. This approach is based on the use of statistical data to evaluate the economic indicators of a region, enterprise, country. The

key methods of this analysis include: analysis of main macroeconomic indicators (GDP, inflation rate, unemployment, export, import, economic growth rates, etc.), analysis of investment flows (assessment of the volume of foreign direct investments coming into the country or region), analysis of the investment structure (identification of sectors receiving the most investments and studying the trends in this structure).

2. Rating method. This method involves creating a ranking of regions or countries or types of economic activities etc. The following groups of indicators can be used: Economic stability: inflation rate, economic growth, level of public debt. Financial attractiveness: tax level, availability of credit resources, inflation expectations. Infrastructure development: availability of transport routes, communications, energy resources. Social development: employment level, average income of the population, access to education and healthcare. Institutional factor: political stability, transparency of the regulatory environment, legal protection of investors.

3. SWOT analysis – this method allows you to assess investment attractiveness by examining internal and external factors. The assessment is based on four components:

- Strengths: advantages of a region or country (e.g. favorable tax policy, access to markets).
- Weaknesses: disadvantages that may deter investment (underdeveloped infrastructure, low-skilled labor force)
- Opportunities: prospects for attracting investment (new markets, investor support programs).
- Threats: external risks, such as political instability, inflation, or changes in international markets .

4. Factor analysis, that allows to identify the main factors that affect the investment attractiveness of a region or country.

5. The index method involves calculating indices based on various indicators that affect investment attractiveness. Such indices may include an index of economic freedom, which includes indicators that characterize the ease of doing business, the level of government intervention, and tax policy.

6. The expert assessment method is based on the opinions of specialists and analysts who evaluate investment attractiveness using qualitative criteria. It can be used to assess risks or forecast market development. For example, experts may evaluate the level of political stability, the growth potential of certain industries, and threats to investors.

7. Comparative analysis (benchmarking) involves comparing the investment attractiveness of one region with other similar regions or countries. Key indicators such as economic growth rates, tax levels, infrastructure provision, political stability, etc., are compared.

8. Risk assessment method - this approach focuses on assessing risks that may affect investment attractiveness.

9. Taxonomic analysis is a method that allows for the classification of regions based on their economic, social, and/or infrastructural characteristics, identifying similarities and differences between them.

The choice of method for assessing the investment attractiveness of regions depends on specific circumstances, such as the research objective, data and resource availability, and the desired level of objectivity and detail in the analysis. However, each of the mentioned methods for assessing investment attractiveness has its advantages and disadvantages, and they are often used in combination to obtain a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of potential opportunities and risks for investors.

It is suggested to use the multidimensional ranking. The regions are evaluated on the following indicators: y_1 – volume of products sold, million UAH; y_2 – capital investments, million UAH; y_3 – number of employed workers, thousand persons; y_4 – loss before taxation, million UAH. Standardization was carried out based on the range of variation

$$Z_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij} - x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \text{ for stimulant indicators;}$$

$$Z_{ij} = \frac{x_{max} - x_{ij}}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \text{ for destimulant indicators.}$$

The volume of products sold, capital investments, and number of employed workers will be stimulant indicators, while loss before taxation will be a destimulant indicator

Fig.1. Top- 5 investment attractiveness regions in 2022

Source: authors' construct based on the data of State Statistics Service of Ukraine [13]

The analysis is conducted across the regions of Ukraine, as this allows for a comprehensive characterization of the functioning of Ukraine's economic system and the patterns of its development.

The outsiders in the ranking are Kherson, Luhansk, and Donetsk regions. Unfortunately, parts of these regions are still under occupation, making any investment activity in those areas impossible. Obviously, their proximity to the front line does not add points. They are less attractive for investment compared to the pre-war period. It is also worth noting that only economic indicators were considered.

In order to analyze the impact of a full-scale invasion on the investment attractiveness of the regions, similar calculations were made based on the data of 2022 using taxonomic analysis (Table 1). However, information on some areas is not published in connection with the fulfillment of the requirements of the Law of Ukraine "On Official Statistics". Therefore, for the possibility of making calculations, the missing values were replaced with empty cells.

Table 1

Economic and Taxonomic Indicators of Enterprise Activity by Ukrainian Region, 2022

Region	Standard scores of indicators				Taxonomic analysis metrics	
	Volume of sold products	Capital investments	Number of employed workers	Loss before taxation	Euclidean distance	Taxonomic indicators
Vinnitsia	0,56	0,43	0,50	0,83	1,52	0,45
Volyn	0,63	0,59	0,65	0,86	1,65	0,40
Dnipropetrovsk	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,00
Donetsk	0,84	0,75	0,76	0,47	1,68	0,39
Zhytomyr	0,74	0,73	0,63	0,87	1,72	0,38
Zakarpattia	0,82	0,70	0,73	1,00	1,80	0,35
Zaporizhzhia	0,63	0,60	0,52	1,00	1,66	0,40
Ivano - Frankivsk	0,77	0,70	0,67	0,69	1,68	0,39
Kyiv	0,14	0,05	0,22	0,33	0,87	0,69
Kirovohrad	0,76	0,69	0,68	0,92	1,75	0,37
Luhansk	1,00	1,00	1,00	0,99	2,00	0,28
Lviv	0,16	0,13	0,15	0,63	1,03	0,63
Mykolayiv	0,78	0,78	0,69	0,50	1,66	0,40
Odesa	0,35	0,45	0,29	1,00	1,44	0,48
Poltava	0,54	0,33	0,42	1,00	1,51	0,46
Rivne	0,79	0,50	0,69	0,72	1,64	0,41
Sumy	0,80	0,76	0,68	0,81	1,75	0,37
Ternopil	0,78	0,63	0,71	0,92	1,74	0,37
Kharkiv	0,41	0,59	0,25	1,00	1,50	0,46

Region	Standard scores of indicators				Taxonomic analysis metrics	
	Volume of sold products	Capital investments	Number of employed workers	Loss before taxation	Euclidean distance	Taxonomic indicators
Kherson	0,99	0,98	0,93	0,81	1,93	0,31
Khmelnysky	0,74	0,58	0,63	0,80	1,66	0,40
Cherkasy	0,57	0,60	0,58	0,69	1,56	0,44
Chernivtsi	0,86	0,85	0,82	0,98	1,88	0,32
Chernihiv	0,81	0,64	0,69	1,00	1,77	0,36

Source: authors' construct based on the data [13,14]

Taxonomic analysis metrics are also visualized in figure 2.

Fig.2. Spider chart of taxonomic analysis metrics

Source: authors' construct based on the data [13, 14]

Despite the full-scale invasion, Dnipropetrovsk, Kyiv, and Lviv regions remained among the leaders, while Luhansk, Kherson, and Chernivtsi regions remained conditional outsiders. It is important to forecast the indices of investment attractiveness in order to manage economic processes in future. Valuable researches

about forecasting are articles of Zomchak, L. and Kukhotska, T. [15], C. -H. Yang and co-authors [16], Duman, G.M. and co-authors [17] and others.

Conclusion. The variety of methods for assessing investment attractiveness makes it a complex choice for researchers, investors, and government officials. However, it is important to note that in certain cases, combining different methods and approaches can be valuable.

Of course, it is necessary to consider various factors, the state of the economic system, and the availability of sufficient data. The use of the ranking method, which is employed in this research, is valuable when it is important to identify outsiders and leaders.

Multidimensional ranking and taxonomic analysis are the methods, which importance in common use and research is necessary for many situations, research fields especially in management, decision making, investment and others.

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